

COMPARISON OF FILM PRESS AND SPRAY APPLICATION OF BIOPOLYMER BARRIER COATINGS ON PAPER

Anna Mayrhofer, Daniel Mandlez, Wolfgang Bauer

Institute of Bioproducts and Paper Technology, Graz University of Technology,
Austria

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10007771
anna.mayrhofer@tugraz.at

1 INTRODUCTION

Paper and board are well-established materials in packaging applications due to their excellent recyclability and biodegradability. Because of their hydrophilicity and porosity modifications are necessary to achieve the desired barrier properties. Especially in food packaging applications, barriers against gases, grease and/or oil are required. These barrier properties are often achieved by the application of layers made from non-renewable materials such as plastics or metal films.

However, these composite materials pose a significant problem for the environment and for the recyclability of fiber-based packaging materials. Naturally occurring biopolymers, such as alginate and chitosan, have shown to be good oxygen and grease barriers. The application of these biopolymers, however, poses several challenges to state-of-the-art paper coating equipment because of the difference in properties compared to conventionally applied paper coating materials. For instance, biopolymers often have a significantly higher viscosity already at low solids content, leading to lower dry application weights and therefore difficulties in reaching the needed film thickness to achieve the targeted barrier properties.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two commercial, sized base papers of different basis weights consisting of either virgin or recycled fibre materials were coated with alginate and chitosan solutions, which were prepared as aqueous solutions at a solids content of 5 wt%.

The application of the biopolymers onto the dry paper webs was performed either with a laboratory film press coating unit (Sumet Technologies) or a purpose-built web spray coating unit (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Spray coating unit.

This spray coating unit consists of a paper web running through the machine and two standard air atomizing nozzles providing independent control of liquid and atomizing air pressure. After coating application, the paper web passes through an infrared drying section with a total of 18 kW drying capacity. Optionally, additional hot air drying is also installed in this spray coating unit. The most relevant machine parameters are liquid pressure, atomizing air pressure and machine speed and those are the ones we focused on in this research. All coating trials were performed to achieve an application weight of approximately 3 g/m² respectively 6 g/m².

The coated samples were tested regarding barrier properties such as air permeability, grease resistance and contact angle.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of these trials show that the application of biopolymers poses several challenges both to the conventional film press and to the alternative coating method. The dry application weight of both biopolymers using a laboratory film press is limited by the low solids content due to the high viscosity of the biopolymers. To obtain higher application weights necessary to achieve the desired barrier properties a second coating layer with a drying step in between is required. In the spray coating unit, the application weight is not limited by the high viscosity of the biopolymers as for film press application. There, the limiting factor at higher application weight seems to be the rewetting of the paper

substrate because of the low solids content of the coating material and the high drying energy needed after the coating. The spray application of the biopolymers results in similar barrier properties as the film press application if the parameters are chosen correctly. The atomizing air pressure must be high enough to guarantee good atomization and therefore small droplets. But the increase in atomizing air pressure is limited by increasing material losses due to misting leading to a significant amount of the biopolymers no longer to land on the substrate. This in turn causes the need for lower machine speeds to achieve the desired application weight. Another option is to increase the liquid pressure which in turn also necessitates a significant increase in the atomizing air pressure.

In upcoming research, the optimization of the spray application is intended by changing the properties of the paper substrates or of the aqueous biopolymer solutions to promote wetting of the paper surface and film formation in order to increase the barrier properties of the spray coatings.